

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Aralova Iroda

AQLI ZAIF BOLALARNI TARBIYALASH VA TA'LIM BERISH, ULARNING MUSTAQIL

FAOLIYATLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA TURLI METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/APREL

